

The Dingxiang Wang Cult

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Dingxiang Wang is a multifaceted deity from the area of Changsha, Hunan, China, who became an important object of Hunanese worship both within and beyond the province in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. The earliest mention of this deity dates back to the Song, during which he was described as the city god (chenghuang) of Tanzhou. He first appeared with frequency in the Qing as a local deity, and then the city god (chenghuang) of Shanhua County, Hunan, which was centered in Changsha. Legends describe him variously as the spirit of an upright demon-quelling official, a flood-calming official, or a locust-eating official, all of whom sacrificed themselves for Changsha. In 1847, he is said to have emerged from the Xiang River and possessed the body of a water-seller, and then marched to the magistrate's yamen and reported for duty as the city god. He thus took on the aspect of a scholar-official, and several accounts indicate that he advised many hopeful participants in the provincial examinations. In 1852, during the Taiping siege of Changsha, Dingxiang Wang was one of at least two deities (including Li Zhenren) whose images were brought to the top of the city walls in an attempt to repel the enemy. Dingxiang Wang was reported to have been effective: When he was turned towards the battlefield, enemy cannon-fire was repelled, and the Taiping soldiers scaling the walls were pushed into midair. His legends state that he manifested as a spectral general who paced the walls and could be seen in a pavilion atop the wall, planning and directing the battle. For this service, Dingxiang Wang received the official moniker "yongzhen." Dingxiang Wang thus became closely associated with the Xiang Army (Hunan Army), a military force that emerged from Changsha-area social networks. Its leaders, including Zeng Guofang and Zuo Zongtang, then received visions and guidance from Dingxiang Wang during their campaigns across the Qing. Dingxiang Wang was known to Xiang Army soldiers not only as a healer, but as a protector, as they fought the Taiping, Nian, and northwestern Muslim rebels all the way to Kashgar in Xinjiang. His worshippers, including the army's leaders but particularly demobilized soldiers, left temples to him across China, where he began to take on other meanings. Dingxiang Wang manifested again in the Sino-French War (1884–1885), in which he protected the coast from foreign cannons, following which he received another title, "fushun." The two known images of him reflect the same combination of aspects: he appears as an upright Confucian scholar-official, but with a tiger skin over his shoulders, indicating military prowess. In Xinjiang, meanwhile, a distinct tradition emerged by the early 1890s—not long after the arrival of Hunanese settlers in 1877—in which the Dingxiang Wang legend was adapted to reflect soldiers' experiences in the borderland, while the deity himself was referred to as "Fangshen." The deity was now said to have been an exiled soldier who, earlier in the Qing, had bravely protected his fellows by diving into a flooded fortress, saving them but sacrificing himself. By the 1910s, he was considered the special city god of Han settlers in Xinjiang. At the same time, he appeared as the protector of Changsha and of Nanjing in the Warlord Era, while newspaper reports indicated that in the 1920s he manifested several times in Changsha in order to punish the wicked. Worship continued in the homeland only until the late 1930s, at which point he fell into obscurity. This was the occasion for the compilation of an important temple gazetteer in Nanjing, where one of his "temporary residences" (xinggong) was very active as a center of Hunanese life. He was still known in Xinjiang into the 1990s. The Dingxiang Wang cult thus defined a complex diasporic community.

Date Range: 1124 CE - 1991 CE

Region: The extent of Dingxiang Wang temples at the end of the Qing

Region tags: Central Asia, China, Xinjiang/East Turkestan

Dingxiang Wang's worship extended far from his original temple in Changsha, Hunan, to the western end of Kashgar and to Fuzhou on the East China Sea. This map includes both those places where he was known as Dingxiang Wang and those in Xinjiang where his worshippers called him "Fangshen."

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schluessel, Eric. "Exiled Gods: Territory, History, Empire, and a Hunanese Deity in Xinjiang." *Late Imperial China* 41, no. 1 (2020): 113-157.
- Source 2: 王鹏辉. 清代民初新疆镇迪道的佛寺道观研究. 乌鲁木齐: 新疆人民出版社, 2016.
- Source 3: 彭明俊, comp. 湖南定湘王南京行宫志略. 南京, 1938.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://collections.lib.uwm.edu/digital/collection/agsphoto/id/8144>
- Source 1 Description: A photograph taken by Helmut De Terra in 1927 or 1928, showing the image of Dingxiang Wang as "Fangshen" in Qarghiliq (Ruoqiang), Xinjiang. This is one of only two known images of the deity.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.zhihu.com/column/p/30686050>
- Source 1 Description: Online article on the remnants of the Dingxiang Wang temple in Changsha, which mostly burnt down in the fire of 1938

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/>
- Source 1 Description: CText is a searchable platform of Chinese texts. It contains occasional references to relevant material. However, I am not aware of any online primary textual corpora that relate specifically to this topic.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang emerged from the multicultural area of Hunan, and then was worshipped extensively in the Muslim-majority region of Xinjiang, where his cult competed for space with mosques and Islamic shrines.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: This is tough, because on the one hand, Dingxiang Wang's worshippers lived among people who followed other religions, often peacefully, but they also competed for space and resources.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Ongoing violent conflict across the Qing was a critical factor in the transformation and spread of the Dingxiang Wang cult.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang's worshippers were among the soldiers who fought against internal and external threats, ranging from the Taiping to the state of Yaqub Beg in Kashgaria to the French invasion.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: This is a complicated question because many of Dingxiang Wang's main worshippers were also significant political and military figures. While that association made sense within what scholars have characterized as the "private bureaucracy" of Zeng Guofan or the "Xiang Army community," it was not official according to the rules or regulations of the Qing empire.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: How are we defining "law" in this database? The answer is non-obvious.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Temples and their endowments could be tax-exempt.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 120000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This question is very difficult to answer, as it presupposes a level of organizational coherence and clarity that you would be hard-pressed to find in many Chinese religious traditions.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Temples and "temporary residences" were headed by managers and councils. The selection process is unclear.

- ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - I don't know
- ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - I don't know
- ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
 - Yes
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
 - No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang's scriptures are transmitted through spirit possession (and thus delivered orally) or through spirit-writing on tablets. They are broadly similar to the other texts concerning morality and eschatology that emerged in the mid-nineteenth-century crisis in the Qing, and they similarly draw upon a common Buddho-Daoist vocabulary suffused with Confucian socio-moral ideals. They include "The Sutra of Rescue from Disaster" 《救劫經》 and the "Message of Awakening from Confusion" 《醒迷文》, both of which were transmitted through spirit-writing. Other scripture-like texts include the deity's various legends about his life and miracles, which are recorded in local gazetteers and in the Nanjing temple gazetteer.

- ↳ Are they written:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they oral:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
 - Yes

Notes: The Nanjing temple gazetteer in particular gathers stories about how Dingxiang Wang transmitted scriptures to the world.

- ↳ Revealed by a high god:
 - No

- ↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
 - Yes

- ↳ Inspired by high god:
 - No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– I don't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends what one means by "institution." Dingxiang Wang mainly scriptures through spirit possession or writing on a spirit-tablet, which were certainly regularized practices. Yet he also revealed himself in dreams and visions.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: I do not have this information on hand, but the size of Dingxiang Wang's main temple can be checked in the "Changsha Prefecture Gazetteer" or "Shanhua County Gazetteer."

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang's temple (miao) in Changsha is quite simply a temple, as befits the city god of a county. However, most of his sites of worship were called "temporary residences" (xinggong), which refers to the places where a deity spends part of their time while on tour of their territory. Dingxiang Wang's "temporary residences" nevertheless became permanent structures.

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Yes, insofar as temples are meant to be sited according to fengshui.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang and others linger in spectral form after death. This belief is common to Chinese religions.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– I don't know

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The afterlife is implicitly present in the scriptures and legends, but it is not discussed at any length.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The general belief in reincarnation is implied in the legends and scriptures, but it is not elaborated upon. This beliefs is common to most Chinese popular religions.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– I don't know

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: In Xinjiang, where Dingxiang Wang's worshippers were usually too poor to pay for their bodies to be brought home for burial, the belief emerged that Dingxiang Wang could send their souls back instead.

↳ Cremation:

– I don't know

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang's worshippers away from Hunan hoped to be buried at home but could rarely afford it. It was thought that Dingxiang Wang would instead send their souls back to Hunan.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- No

Are grave goods present:

- No

Are formal burials present:

- I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

- Yes

- ↳ A supreme high god is present:

- Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang was certainly conceived of as a powerful deity, although I would place him within the broader understanding of the bureaucratic spiritual world headed by the Jade Emperor. Other deities were powerful. Dingxiang Wang himself was often accompanied by the Thunder God, Li Zhenren, or the mysterious "Dingxiang Wang Niangniang," a feminine figure who had a different birthday. Indeed, Dingxiang Wang seems to mirror Li Zhenren (a local immortal) who was joined in eternity by his sister. In the legends and rituals of Dingxiang Wang, we can see reflections of the apotheosized Qu Yuan and of the general complex of water-related stories and beliefs from the area of Changsha and Lake Dongting. Later on, in Xinjiang Dingxiang Wang was seen as the specific god of Hunanese settlers, while Han from other parts of China had their own local gods. Gradually, he became the chief Han deity in Xinjiang, who was uniquely able to transmit messages and souls back to the inner provinces.

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

- Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

- No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

- No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - I don't know
 - Notes: This is a confusing question in the context of Chinese religion. The deity in question has a title, wang, that is often translated as "king," but he was never, to my knowledge, granted that title by an earthly power.
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Dingxiang Wang combines the aspects of a flood-pacifying spirit, a scholar-official city god, and a military deity.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Dingxiang Wang pacifies floods, defends settlements, gives aid in battle, defends the Qing and China, punishes immorality, and turns away locusts.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: There are several stories of Dingxiang Wang appearing in front of an immoral person in Changsha—usually a thief or murderer—and beating them into submission until they repent for their crimes.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: There are several accounts of manifestation in dreams. One interesting instance of dream communication took place when Zuo Zongtang, then leader of the Xiang Army, lost one of his chief officers, Liu Songshan. Dingxiang Wang commanded Zuo in a dream to appoint Liu Songshan's nephew Liu Jintang to his office. Liu Jintang later experienced a dream in which Dingxiang Wang assured him of his success.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The primary known means by which Dingxiang Wang sent messages to his worshippers was through spirit-writing, in which someone enters a trance state, and they or a helper records their words through a stylus on a board covered in sand. It is probable that this is how Zeng Guofan and Zuo Zongtang mainly interacted with him, as Zeng at least is known to have engaged in spirit-writing, and legends of Dingxiang Wang include people conducting this ritual at his temple.

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang himself, like many Chinese deities, is a "previously human spirit." The legends of his origins can vary considerably, but they all associate him with a figure who sacrificed himself for the good of the community.

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: A significant story about Dingxiang Wang's origins says that, in life, he was an upright official and descendant of an important Tang-era Confucian who was skilled at detecting and quelling demons.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends what you mean by "mixed human-divine beings." See the concept of apotheosis in China.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As noted elsewhere, Dingxiang Wang did not usually travel alone. He was worshipped alongside the various deities of popular Chinese religion, and temples to Wenchang or Guandi were often attached to his own. Dingxiang Wang Niangniang was worshipped with him in several places. Very intriguingly, in at least one temple in Xinjiang, Dingxiang Wang was worshipped alongside Fangshen, his local variant.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– I don't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Dingxiang Wang explicitly protects his worshippers in battle.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang punishes thieves.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang has revealed through spirit-writing that he wants his worshippers to adhere to the Confucian rites.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang punished people for murder, theft, and disrespecting his temple. Punishments included sickness and beatings.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang bestowed mainly success in battle upon his adherents, as well as a means for one's soul to be reunited with one's family.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang is described as returning order to a chaotic world.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Dingxiang Wang appears and reappears. There is no sense of a fixed apocalypse, but rather of the continual renewal of the world. See Vincent Goossaert's work on models of eschatology in the nineteenth century.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– No

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: Revival of proper ritual and socio-moral order across China.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Xiang Army's regulations included a strict moral code, which was in turn associated with Dingxiang Wang worship. The code included prohibitions against unfair bargaining at the market, plundering and looting, opium smoking, and other vices one might expect from soldiers.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is necessary for participants in the sacrifices to Dingxiang Wang on his birthday.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– I don't know

Notes: This is complicated, because we can distinguish between Dingxiang Wang's general worshippers in and around Changsha (who were laypeople) and his worshippers in the Xiang Army, who were required to conform to ethical precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Dingxiang Wang's birthday is on the twenty-eighth day of the fifth lunar month. (Dingxiang Wang Niangniang's is on the fifteenth day of the second lunar month.) His temple festival was by all accounts an especially raucous affair, for which the temple's custodians and their chosen helpers would prepare three days in advance. A series of sacrifices was made under the direction of the manager: One sheep and one pig were sacrificed. On the previous day, at the third hour of the morning, the temple manager would light incense, burn candles, light firecrackers, ring bells, beat drums, and slaughter the animals. One pan each of sheep and pig's blood would be offered to Dingxiang Wang, and the other two to Dingxiang Wang Niangniang. The next morning, at the formal sacrifice, two banquet would be laid before either figure. The manager would divide up the pig and sheep to distribute among the attendants and board members. Notably, the Niangniang's birthday feast was vegetarian, involving fruit and wheaten foods in place of the meat. Participant recited rhyming texts recounting Dingxiang Wang's deeds and miracles.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Notes: It depends.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: This question is confusing. Dingxiang Wang is primarily worshipped on two specified days each year.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A significant body of Dingxiang Wang's worshippers were members of the Xiang Army or their descendants.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: It possesses a formal calendar in the sense of a liturgical calendar, which is in turn guided by the Chinese lunar calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Eric Schluessel. Exiled Gods: Territory, History, Empire, and a Hunanese Deity in Xinjiang. *Late Imperial China*, 41(1) doi: 10.1353/late.2020.0002.